

Pontificate and Antipotificates - Tripapism in the 15th century, from the Council of Pisa to the Council of Constance

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A little-known episode about the Middle Ages is the Tripapism that occurred at the beginning of the 15th century. A time when there were three distinct pontifical lineages, with each pontiff officially elected by a collegiate of cardinals, each leading entire peoples and kingdoms, who swore allegiance to him. Although tripapism is a short-lived phenomenon, 9 years (between the years 1408 and 1417) it allows us a deeper reflection on the ecclesiastical power of the medieval Catholic Church.

It is common knowledge that the Catholic Church would have had an almost hegemonic power during the Middle Ages, certainly having disputes with secular powers, as in the case of the Investiture Quarrel. It is also common knowledge that the Catholic Church had internal disputes over power. However, officially, its uniqueness, according to the common census, had always been guaranteed by the papal figure. So, officially, to this day, one can easily find a papal lineage defended by the Catholic Church where we have a perfect and uninterrupted line from Peter to the current pontiff.

The existence of antipopes is certainly recognized by the Church. Officially, an antipope is a false pope, who proclaims himself as leader of the Church, without having been canonically elected by a council of cardinals,

or according to the customs of the Church¹. At all times when there are two popes, each considers himself the true pope, the title of *antipope* is only established after the reunification of a split in the Church, since the winning side is able to officially declare the losing side as antipope, while the official lineage is established through the winning group. But we must bear in mind that while the dispute is still ongoing it is practically impossible for the faithful to define which side will be the winner, and therefore, to discern who will have the official title and who will be considered the antipope.

According to Hergenröther^{two} we have, for example, between the years 1159 and 1180, a lineage of antipopes composed of four “antipontiffs” (Victor IV, 1159-64, Pascal III, 1164-68, Callixtus III, 1168-77, Innocente III, 1178- 80), making it clear that, in addition to the episode presented in this article, we have several other moments in history where different pontifical lineages were established for a relatively large number of years or decades.

Despite there being almost a hundred official antipopes cataloged by the Catholic Church, tripapism is extremely rare, even more so lasting for several years. Since the establishment of three pontifical lineages implies that we have either two splits at different times, or a major split that allows the creation of three pontiffs, all declaring themselves officially elected by the collegiate of cardinals.

The tripontificate of the early 15th century has its roots in an older and definitely more complex episode in the history of the Church, the Western Schism, which in turn has its origins in another older episode, the Papacy of Avignon (1309- 1377). Several historians specialized in the history of the Catholic Church define the period between 1050 and 1300 as a marked era for the growth of clerical power, at the same time that this, when expanding, caused major conflicts with secular power and the emergence of powerful popular heresies. RW Southern, in his *The history of the*

¹*New Advent Encyclopedia*,v. Antitoppe

^{two}Cardinal official historian of the Church in the 19th century, responsible for organizing vast documentary material of the Catholic Church.

church – Western society and the church in the middle ages³ defines this period as *The Age of Growth*. Other authors have less pompous names, such as Donald Logan⁴ which uses the era of crisis between Church and State or even Brian Tierne⁵ who produces an entire work with this title. According to Nachman Falbel⁶, the 12th and 13th centuries could be called heretical centuries, when considering only the history of the Western church.

Since a decree by Pope Nicholas II in 1059, the papal election was the responsibility of only the cardinals and the conclave was established. According to Southern, the act that wanted to exclude secular influence from the papal election ended up becoming a fallacy, since instead of removing secular influence, it only replaces the influence in the figure of kings or emperors, with secular influence within the collegiate of cardinals. , leaving these elections tense, decisive, but at the same time secret, giving them a greater tone of sacredness. In 1296, Pope Boniface VIII was involved in a dispute with Philip IV of France, also known as Philip the Fair. This, with the support of civil jurists, sought to reduce papal power over France as much as possible, among his measures is, for example, the clerical tax⁷. Boniface VIII issued two bulls to expand his power over France, *Laic Clerics*, which prevented secular lords from taxing the Church, and later, the famous Bull *Unam sanctam*, which defends the unity of the Church, and above all, the unity of its control, in the supremacy of power of the Pope.

When Pope Boniface VIII dies in 1303, Pope Benedict XI takes over, who remains in the papacy for only 8 months, probably having been killed by poisoning. Between the years 1304 and 1305 we have a papal interregnum, the

³SOUTHERN, R.W. *The history of the church – Western Society and the church in the middle ages*, P. 34

⁴LOGAN, Donald, *A history of the church in the middle ages*, p.129

⁵TIERNEI, Brian, *The Crisis of Church and State 1050-1300*

⁶FALBEL, Nachman, *Medieval Heresies*, P. 13

⁷DAMEROW, Harold, *Avignon Papacy*, in http://faculty.ucc.edu/egh-damerow/avignon_papacy.htm

The dispute between French cardinals and Roman cardinals had reached several impasses regarding the succession. Finally, in June 1305 Raymond Bertrand de Got, French cardinal, was elected pope, supported by the French cardinals, assuming the papacy under the name of Clement V. This papal election itself was surrounded by great tension⁸. Firstly, the conclave took place in Perugia, the city where Benedict XI officially died, although the chronicler of the time Giovanni Villani states that he died in Nogaret, land of William of Nogaret, right-hand man of Philip IV of France. As a second point, the same chronicler states that, before the papal election, King Felipe IV himself would have been seen next to Bertrand, making a vow of loyalty to him.

In any case, after the conclave and the election of Clement V, he moved to France, and later, in 1309, ordered the move of the entire capital of the church to Avignon. Thus officially beginning the Avignon papacy. During this period the headquarters of the Church was transferred to the French city, the controversial episode that occurred during the papacy of Clement V, would establish an Avignon papal lineage that would last 6 papal successions. The establishment of the church's headquarters in Avignon had several consequences, among them, the strengthening of French influence within the Catholic Church (all 6 popes elected at this time were French and 111 of the 134 cardinals appointed were French) at the same time that it brought diverse voices contrary to change, especially to the intense luxury and pomp that the clergy lived in France, as in the case of the famous Italian scholar Francesco Petrarca (1304-1374) who went on to define: "*Now I'm living in France, the Babylon of the West. (...) Here reign the successors of the poor Fishermen of Galilee, they have strangely forgotten their origin. I am amazed when I remember their predecessors, to see these men laden with gold and dressed in purple, proud of their spoils of princes and peoples, to see these luxurious palaces reaching the heights and crowned with fortifications, instead of seeing boats turned upside down to serve as a shelter*"⁹. The material power and luxury of the Avignon papacy is criticized by several

⁸NELSON, Lynn H. *The Avignon Papacy*, in <http://www.the-orb.net/textbooks/nelson/avignon.html>

⁹H Robinson, *Readings in European History* (Boston: 1904), p. 502.

other contemporaries, such as the English theologian, Wycliffe, professor at Oxford, who declares: "*Christ didn't exactly have any possessions, he declares that he didn't even have a place to lay his head, but men say that this pope has more than half the empire, with pride and pomp. Christ was the weakest and most humble of men, he only used a cloth to cover his body and washed the feet of his disciples, as John's gospel tells us. The Pope, sitting on his throne, makes the lords kiss his feet. Christ went everywhere, preaching the gospel and helping the poor, the pope, whether he lives in Avignon or not, does exactly the opposite.*"¹⁰

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We have in the pontificate of Gregory XI¹¹ the beginning of the attempt to return to Rome, which would cause the Great Schism of the West. Despite this, we cannot see a weakening of the papacy, on the contrary, the papacy became so powerful that, being intensely more disputed, almost like an imperial head, it allowed internal disputes and civil wars.

After assuming the papacy in 1370, supported by the French monarchy, like previous popes, he wished to expand his power over the easternmost region, especially after previous popes' disagreements with the region of Italy and the Holy Empire. However, the expansion of its power in Italy and the use of military force to expand its domains in this region generated a war that was a little more complex than expected. Florence and Milan unite in 1372, in disputes against Gregory XI. Several other cities that had recently been conquered by the papacy and integrated into the Papal States joined the alliance of Florence and Milan, such as Bologna, Perugia, Orvieto and Viterbo. Pope Gregory XI's response was the massive excommunication of everyone involved in this uprising, as well as the excommunication of the entire city of Florence and a blockade of it. It was also ordered to withhold all the assets of all Florentines throughout Europe. This measure, however, caused a furor among bankers in Avignon, so that the French king, Charles V, himself decided to disregard the blockade. Roberto de

¹⁰WYCLIFFE, John, *From Officio Pastoralis*, chapter 32

¹¹Between 1370 and 1378

Geneva, future antipope Clement VII, leads Gregory XI's army, advancing on the alliance of Italian cities, defeating the rebels.

It was then that Pope Gregory the French king himself had disrespected his blockade order, even though he did not impose any official sanctions on it.

The pope's arrival in Rome was tense, with people being mysteriously poisoned and shipwrecked, until he arrived safely in Rome on January 17, 1378. However, two months after his arrival, he died on March 27. of the same year. He was probably poisoned. After his death, great pressure began from the Roman people to hold a conclave in Rome. In this conclave, Pope Urban VI was elected. However, the French cardinals returned to Avignon, under the command of Robert of Geneva, and with the support of the French king, they elected Robert as pope, taking the title of Clement VII.

Then begins, in 1378, the Great Schism of the West, where two independent papal lineages will be formed. A large number of kingdoms will ally themselves with each of these popes, so that the lineage and pontifical power of each of them will survive after his death in new conclaves, each of them claiming to be legitimate. Even though officially, after the end of the Schism, the Catholic Church declared that the popes of Rome were the officers and the popes of Avignon were actually antipopes, such a declaration is only possible because, at the council of Constance, which puts an end to the split, the Roman side ends up winning and little by little the persecution of destruction of the popes of Avignon continues (which remains in a lineage even after this council). Otherwise, the popes of the Roman line would certainly be called antipopes.

Below is a small table demonstrating the alliances made around each pope:

<i>Avignon Papacy</i>	<i>Roman Papacy</i>
<i>France, Aragon, Chatelaine, Lion, Cyprus, Burgundy, Savoy, Naples and Scotland.</i>	<i>Denmark, England, Flanders, Holy Empire, Hungary, Italian cities north of the Papal States, Norway, Poland and Sweden</i>

In this way we also have two different papal lineages¹²

<i>Avignon Papacy</i>	<i>Roman Papacy</i>
<i>Clement VII (1378-1394)</i>	<i>Urban VI (1378-1389)</i>
<i>Benedict XIII (1394-1423)</i>	<i>Boniface IX (1389-1404)</i>
<i>Clement VIII (1423-1429)</i>	<i>Innocent VII (1404-1406)</i>
<i>Benedict XIV (Bernard Garnier) 1424-1430</i>	<i>Gregory XII (1406-1414)</i>
<i>Benedict XIV (John Carrier) 1424-1437</i>	<i>Martin V (1417-1431)</i>

During the Schism, several attempts were made to reunite the Church. Several unification speeches had already taken place in the years close to the beginning of the Schism, other small councils had already been held in Ghent and Florence, and discussions about reunification were carried out by the University of Orxford and the University of Paris, meetings that were attended by the presence of renowned doctors such as Henry of Langenstein in two epistles: *Pacis Epistle* from 1379, and *Epistle concilii pacis* of 1381 or Conrad of Gelnhausen in his *Epistle Concordiae* in

¹²The lineages presented here include those applicants for the position of pontiff even after the Council of Constance, which reunited the church. This is because, despite dissident lineages finding little secular support, they continued to exist and attempt to reassert themselves until two decades after reunification in 1414–1418.

1380 and also Jean de Charlier de Gerson, professor at the University of Paris, in his *Sermo coram Anglicis*, produced approximately 1391. Even in the following century, more than two decades after the Schism, there were still strong speeches regarding unification, such as Pierre d'Ailly, bishop of Cambrai, who wrote *At first schismatis materiam concilii generalis primus instanter prosequi non timui*.¹³

The University of Paris itself, in 1393, had already produced a document, probably at the request of King Charles VI, of France, proposing three possible solutions to the impasse of separation from the Church: "*The first way for the Schism to end would be for each side to completely renounce and relinquish all legal rights that they claim over themselves and for a new pope to be elected. (...) The second, if both tenaciously refused to resign, as they have done up until now, that a form of arbitration be placed upon him, so that they would choose tenacious men of great value, allowing them to argue both for regular law, as well as canon law, giving them full authority to discuss and carry out the chosen decision with them in accordance with canon law (...) in this way they could properly proceed with the papal election. (...) The third way, if the rival popes do not accept to act in a friendly way or as brothers, and do not accept the forms proposed above, we propose an excellent remedy to this sacrilegious schism. (...) We refer to a general Council, composed in accordance with canon law, with the presence only of prelates, or as many are illiterate or are merely supporters of one pope or another, that only the prelates who are masters and doctors in theology or laws from the faculties of approved universities.*"¹⁴

In this way we can see that even a decade and a half before the Council of Pisa, there was already an intention on the part of some thinkers

¹³Published in 2010 via facsimile edition in *1409 In Italy: Council Of Pisa, Battle Of Sanluri*, Paperback, Books Llc's Photocopy Edition

¹⁴THATCHER, Oliver J. & MCNEAL, Edgar Holmes (eds), *A Source Book for Medieval History*, (New York: Scribners, 1905), p. 326-327

French in creating a new council and the possibility of a new papal election. It is important to highlight that, despite the idea of unification, there were already indications that this new election might not be universally accepted, this can be seen by the suggestion that the illiterate and supporters of the old popes should not be summoned to this new council, so that, it could be assumed that both the pontiffs would not accept such a council, as the document itself proposes, and equally, they would have support from the tops of their churches (even though these supporters were considered, by the University of Paris, as illiterate or partisans who would not act by reason)

In 1408, a group of cardinals of the French lineage, with support from the University of Paris, left for Livorno to meet with cardinals of the Roman lineage, trying to create a meeting that could reunite the papacy. Following the meeting of these four French cardinals with the Romans, a general council was scheduled for March 25, 1409, in Pisa. This council received immediate approval from Charles VI, of France, support from the universities of Paris and Oxford, and from some of the aforementioned doctors, such as d'Ailly and Gerson. Other monarchs offered support in a less formal way, such as Henry IV of England¹⁵

The Council was attended by 24 cardinals (14 of the Roman lineage and 10 of the Avignon lineage) 80 bishops, 87 abbots, 4 patriarchs, 41 worse, 100 representatives of bishops and 300 doctors of theology or canon law.

About the council we have the following document:

"This sacred and general council, representing the Universal Church, decrees and declares that the united college of cardinals has been appointed for the convocation of the council, and that the power of convening the council belongs to this said sacred college of Cardinals, especially now during this detestable Schism. The College of Cardinals also declares that this sacred Council is representative of the universal Catholic Church, and that both claimants to the

¹⁵HARVEY, Margaret, *Nicholas Ryssheton and the Council of Pisa, 1409*pp. 197-208

papal throne were mentioned at the gates and doors of the churches of Pisa, so that they could come and hear our final decision regarding the schism and justify themselves so that this sentence would not be applied to them.

All of us cardinals, and the bishops and priests and deacons of the Holy Roman Catholic Church, are gathered in the city of Pisa, for the purpose of ending the Schism and restoring the unity of the Church, in accordance with the honorable promise of God, which is the Holy Roman Catholic Church. This council now declares that until one of us is elected pope, we will continue to represent the Church through this collegiate and will not dissolve it, and will not allow it to be dissolved, until the universal reformation of the Church and of its head and its members is finalized."¹⁶

It is interesting to note that the collegiate of cardinals does not speak of the abdication of both popes so that there could be the choice of a unified pontiff, on the contrary, it places both popes only as suitors. Although there is no clear justification for this position, it is possible that, by denying the existence of a pope, power in the hands of the collegiate of cardinals and a new pontifical election would easily be justifiable. On the contrary, if there were really two "popes" it would be necessary for both of them to abdicate for a new election to take place.

A second aspect that deserves to be highlighted is that the said Council would not be dissolved not only until a new pontiff was elected, but until the reform of the Church, both its head and its members, was completed. What reform did the council refer to? If this reform was reunification, why not use the term "reunification" or something more precise? Perhaps a clue to this position is the opening of the Council of Constance, as we will see later.

After about 3 months, on June 5, the Council of Pisa issued a condemnation of both popes for refusing to accept reconciliation. Both Benedict XIII (Pope of Avignon) and Gregory XII (Pope of Rome) were

¹⁶Chronicle of Raynaldus - 1409, in THACHER & MCNEAL, *A Source Book for Medieval History*, P. 327-328.

considered heretics, for perpetuating a Schism that divided the Church, and considered guilty of perjury, for having broken their vows to serve the Church.

List of cardinals who elect Alexander V, Pope of Pisa

Cardinal of lineage Roman	Date on which became cardinal	Cardinal of lineage of Avignon	Date on which became cardinal
<i>Enrico Minutoli</i> (Director of college of cardinals)	December 18 from 1389	<i>Malsec Guide</i> (Director of college of cardinals)	December 20 from 1375
<i>Antonio Caetani</i>	February 27, 1402	<i>Niccolò Brancaccio</i>	December 18 from 1378
<i>Angelo d'Anna Sommariva</i>	December 17th from 1384	<i>Jean de Brogny</i>	July 12, 1385
<i>Corrado Caraccioli</i>	June 12, 1405	<i>Pierre Girard</i>	October 17, 1390
<i>Francesco Ugucione</i>	June 12, 1405	<i>Pierre de Thury</i>	July 12, 1385
<i>Giordano Orsini</i>	June 12, 1405	<i>Pedro Fernández</i> from Frías	January 23, 1394
<i>Giovanni Migliorati</i>	June 12, 1405	<i>Amadeo Saluzzo</i>	December 23 from 1383
<i>Pietro Filargo</i> (elected pope Alexander V)	June 12, 1405	<i>Pierre Blain</i>	December, 24 from 1395
<i>Antonio Calvi</i>	June 12, 1405	<i>Louis deBar</i>	December 21 from 1397
<i>Landolfo Maramaldo</i>	December 21 from 1381	<i>Antonio de Challant</i>	May 9, 1404
<i>Rinaldo</i>	December 17th		

<i>Branaccio</i>	from 1384	
<i>Baldassare Cossa</i>	February 27, 1402	
<i>Oddone Colonna</i>	June 12, 1405	
<i>Pietro Stefaneschi</i>	June 12, 1405	

A closer look at the table above demonstrates some unusual elements. Especially the fact that 8 of the 14 cardinals of the Roman lineage became cardinals on the same day, June 12, 1405. At the same time, from the Avignon lineage we have cardinals markedly appointed right at the beginning of the Schism, or even before it. The fact that more than half of the Roman cardinals were named on the same day may become even more striking if we consider who appointed them. In the Roman lineage, during the period of the schism, we have 4 popes, however only one of them, Innocent VII, had an intensely short pontificate, restricted almost practically to the year 1405, where he appointed nine cardinals, two of which eight were present at the Council of Pisa.

Innocent VII, whose birth name was Cosimo de' Migliorati, was appointed by Pope Boniface IX, with the main mission of participating in negotiations with the Avignon papacy. These negotiations had the opportunity to put an end to the schism when in 1404, Boniface IX died, while some cardinals from Avignon were in Rome, and Innocent VII proposed that instead of holding a conclave to elect a new Roman pontiff, the Pope of Avignon, Benedict XIII, resigned and then the cardinals of both lineages came together for a single conclave where a pope would be elected who would once again unify the Church. On the occasion of Benedict XIII's denial, the conclave took place involving only the Roman cardinals (only 8 cardinals were present), and Cosimo was elected Pope Innocent VII. Even after being elected, he declared that he would accept to abdicate his position if Benedict XIII did the same or did so, so that a new conclave could take place. On the occasion of the Pope's new denial of Avignon, Innocent appointed 8 cardinals

presented above. The high number of nominations, including the nomination of his nephew: Ludovico Migliorati. Innocent VII saw a revolt against his power in the city of Rome, in particular because of Ladislaus's attempts to expand from Naples to the city of Rome. In a turbulent period, both from an ecclesiastical point of view and from the secular power in territorial disputes on the Italian peninsula, Innocent VII's papacy ended in 1406.

Before the conclave meeting in 1406, the cardinals expressly declared that they would only agree to hold the papal election if the chosen one was willing to meet with his rival, from the Avignon lineage, to reach the end of the Schism. However, after the election of Gregory XII, who would have accepted these conditions, the same pontiff denies such a meeting, justifying that it would be dangerous to leave Rome until Ladislaus was defeated. This temporarily puts an end to negotiation efforts on the part of the pontiffs, especially during the pontificate of Innocent VII.

In this way, when we analyze both the list of cardinals present at the Council of Pisa and electors of Alexander V, Pope of Pisa, as well as the epistles produced by theologians from both Oxford and Paris, we have clear elements to affirm that the idea of electing a The third pontiff, who would put an end to the Schism, is not Pisa's creation nor is he part of a minority group. Likewise, we can verify that, even before the council actually took place, it already represented a third group that in some way was already dissenting in thought from the other two. On the one hand, it is precisely from the University of Paris that the idea of electing a third pontiff comes from, it is from France that the cardinals come from who will generate the idea of the Council of Pisa, meeting with the Romans so that the whole process can begin. But at the same time, it is precisely the Avignon papacy that denies the Roman proposals for a unified conclave where the schism could be ended. In order to demonstrate that there was a dissident group in France that did not support the schism. In the same way, we have in the figure of Pope Innocent VII the great Roman attempt at unification, at the same time, his pontificate is short and his successor does not resume his attempts at reunification, even so, half of the Roman cardinals present at his council were chosen specifically

by Innocent VII in his short pontificate, demonstrating that there was a difference in the thoughts of these cardinals to the elected pontiff, who refused to comply with the guidelines of the collegiate of cardinals himself at the time of his conclave.

The election of Alexander V, as Pope of Pisa, gives voice to this group that was formed by both supporters of Avignon and supporters of Rome, but in a certain way opposed the stances of the pontificates of both trends. However, Alexander V, who was one of the cardinals appointed by Innocent VII during his pontificate, also suffered an intensely short pontificate, lasting just 10 months, having been found together with Baldassare Cossa, the aforementioned cardinal present at the council, coming from Rome (but not one of the 8 cardinals named by Innocent VII) and who would become John XXIII, after the second conclave of Pisa.

After the election of John XXIII as Pope of Pisa, we have the issue of secular support divided between the three pontiffs, demonstrating that the split was much deeper than it might previously appear:

Kingdoms loyalty to the papacy of Rome	what swore loyalty to the Avignon papacy	Kingdoms loyalty to the papacy of Pisa
Naples ¹⁷ , Poland and most of the Holy Empire	Bavaria, Aragon, Scotland	France, Bohemia, Portuguese, Florence, Venice, Pisa, plus a small part of the Holy Empire

For 6 years we have had these three pontifical currents following each other distinctly, even though it was already becoming clear that the Avignon lineage was beginning to lose strength. The tripartition of the Catholic Church

¹⁷Led by the same Ladislaus, who had fought against Innocent VII, but who allied himself with Benedict XIII

it would last until the Council of Constance (1414-1418), which would also be tense and full of unexpected turns.

The Council was convened by the Pope of Pisa, John XXIII and supported by King Sigismund of Bohemia, Croatia and Hungary (and later Holy Roman Emperor). Empire), this begins on November 16, 1414, in the cathedral of the city of Constance, in the Holy Empire (a city currently on the border between Germany and Switzerland).

Below is the transcript of the opening speech¹⁸ given by Bishop John. According to Jacques Lenfant and Stephen Whatley¹⁹, although there were two other bishops named John, John, bishop of Geneva or John, bishop of Litchfield, both present at the opening of the council. Most likely he was referring to Pope John XXIII himself, the Pope of Pisa who convenes the council. Since the pope always carries with him the title of Bishop of Rome, even in this case, where the pope who initiated the council was the one whose headquarters were in the city of Pisa. The term *Servant of the Servants of God*, clearly indicates that it was not a matter of any other disposition, but certainly of the pontiff himself.

“First section, which took place on November 16, 1414,

John, bishop, servant of the servants of God, so that it may be recorded for posterity, wishing to carry forward what was decreed at the council of Pisa, by his predecessor of joyful memory, Pope Alexander V, convenes a new general council, which had previously already had been summoned by letters sent by us, to deal with the matters described below:

We all come to you, venerable brethren, cardinals of the holy Roman Church, and to the court of the city of Constance, at this present hour, to present here, by the Grace of God, what

¹⁸The acts of the Council were first published in 1500 by Jerome of Croatia in *Acta scitu dignissima docteque concinnata Constantiensis concilii celebratissimi*

¹⁹LENFANT, Jacques & WHATLEY, Stephen, *The history of the Council of Constance*, p.187

now we will do, desiring the advice of this synod, to achieve peace, exaltation and reform of the Church and thus silence the Christian people.

In this pressing matter it is not right to rely on the strength of a single person, but instead to place our trust in God. In this way, to begin with our divine worship, we decree, with the approval of this sacred council, a special mass for the purpose of what will be said today. This mass will not be celebrated in vain, by the grace of God. We now decree that this mass be celebrated by the collegiate present here or by other collegiate churches in this city, whether secular or regular, once a week, always on Friday, while the sacred council is in session. Furthermore, we command a faithful devotion to this celebration with the greatest fervor, so that they can feel refreshed by the abundant divine grace, and then we can relax in the hands of the merciful God because of the great amount of penance that each one confesses at each mass. . One year of penance for the priest who is celebrating the mass and forty days for all who are present. Furthermore, we exhort our venerable brethren, the cardinals of the church of Rome, as well as the patriarchs, archbishops and bishops and our beloved children, the abbots and other clergy, to devoutly celebrate this mass once a week, so that the Divine providence may be upon us as we plead for it, and we will grant the same indulgences to the celebrant and to all who are present at the mass.

We urge the Lord even more, for the glory of the name of Christ, that we may have a grand outcome on the issues we will deal with, and may diligently give prayers and fasting to those who have a holy work. May God put upon them humility and then great joy will begin in this sacred encounter.

Considering, above all, the matters that this council considers threats to the Catholic faith, in accordance with the practices that have already occurred in previous councils, and knowing that these things demand diligence, time for study and that they are matters of intense difficulty, we urge for all who are versed in the sacred scriptures to ponder this threat, and that everyone can discuss it with each other, and that they can contribute ideas that are useful and timely for this subject. Let us call these issues before us here in this sacred synod, for we can convincingly resolve these issues. And in due time we will be able to decide and repudiate whatever is necessary, for the profit and growth of the Catholic faith.

In particular, we will need to ponder several errors that are being spread in various places and at different times, especially by those who claim to have knowledge of the works of one John Wycliffe.²⁰

It is common, at the beginning of a council, to have an opening speech with an appeal for union and submission to God's designs. But we cannot fail to highlight the urgent and special nature of this appeal, both due to the issue of penances, and the appeal that all those versed in the sacred scriptures and not just the bishops and cardinals could participate diligently in resolving the problems in question, that is , the entire character of the opening speech demonstrates great concern and urgency in resolving these problems. Imagining a tripartite church, the urgency is justifiable. However, at the end of the appeal, before any question related to the pontificates, before any question related to the churches based in Avignon and Rome, we have a special request for consideration of John Wycliffe's thoughts, demonstrating that these thoughts, in

²⁰"Complete Acts of Council of Constance" in <http://www.dailycatholic.org/history/16ecume1.htm>

At the time, they were considered at least as serious as the division of power within the church.

But who was John Wycliffe, who is mentioned in the opening speech of the Council that was supposed to reunify the tripartite Church? He is an English theologian, professor at Oxford, who lived in the 14th century, considered a heretic, widely critical of the religious institution, even declaring the impossibility of an institutional church in his work. *The Wicket*²¹. It is important to remember that the speech presented here was given by the Pope of Pisa, John XXIII, successor of Alexander V, the same pope elected by the group of cardinals who speaks of the importance of a reform of the entire Church, beyond its head, as we have seen at the opening of the Council of Pisa. Likewise, for this council, Jan Hüs, a theologian from Bohemia, who had contact with Wycliffe's ideas through Jerome of Prague, was specially summoned. The role of this theologian was precisely to explain and defend Wycliffe's ideas before the Council. However, a more detailed explanation of this issue will not be possible in this article.²².

Regardless of the original idea of convening the Council of Constance, it will take a completely different direction than expected. This occurs because, after the opening of the Council of Constance by Pope John XXIII of Pisa, on November 16, 1414, the next citation that appears in the council's records is only from March 2, 1415. However, the record with this The date is intensely brief, he talks about the resignation of Pope John XXIII and mention of him simply abandoning Constance, probably considered an escape.

There are several theories that try to explain the resignation of Pope John XXIII. The most commonly accepted is that he would have agreed to resign if the other two popes also resigned, so that a new pope could be elected during the council. In this way, he would have accepted

²¹AZEVEDO, Leandro Villela de, *The English Works of John Wycliffe inserted in the religious context of his time: From the Summa Theologiae of Aquinas to the Council of Constance, From the Franciscan Spirituals to William of Ockham*, p.336

²²To this end, we suggest the author's doctoral thesis, cited in the previous note.

resign on March 2nd²³. However, this theory does not explain why only John XXIII resigned on that day and especially does not explain why, shortly after his resignation, he fled disguised as a messenger. There is also the theory that he, having resigned before the cardinals, demonstrated that he had more interest in resolving the situation of the church than in maintaining power, but as the one who presided over the council, even after his resignation from the pontifical position, being a bishop, would continue the discussions²⁴. In this case, the escape would have occurred only when, upon resigning, he would have begun to suffer persecution and also abandon the council, which would have caused him to flee.

Although this last theory has more foundation, there is no denying the possibility that the Council was taken over, in a certain way, by supporters opposed to the ideas of John XXIII

. Let us see, therefore, the continuation of the acts of the council, already under the command of Pope Gregory XII²⁵:

Decrees on the integrity and authority of the council, after the pope's trip²⁶.

For honor, we praise and glorify the most sacred trinity: Father Son and Holy Spirit, and to obtain on Earth, for people of good will, the peace that was definitively promised to the Church of God, this sacred synod convened by the general council of Constança, duly gathered here by the Holy Spirit, with the purpose of bringing unity and reform to the said

²³MIRANDA, Salvador, *The Life of Antipope John XXIII* in <http://www2.fiu.edu/~mirandas/bios1419.htm>

²⁴LENFANT, Jacques & WHATLEY, Stephen, *The history of the Council of Constance*, p.120

²⁵Who would also resign a few weeks later, beginning a period of papal interregnum that will last 2 years, until the election of Martin V

²⁶Certainly referring to the departure of Pope John XXIII. It is important to highlight that at no point does the document give the idea of it being an escape but rather just a "trip".

church, its head and members discerningly declare, define and command the following:

The change in language is easily noticed. While Pope John XXIII spoke, the speech was the exchange of ideas, prayer and the good will to define a dialogue, while now, the first opening made by Pope Gregory XII comes, in its first paragraph, with a speech imperative to define, declare and order, and no longer discuss.

Here is the sequence of orders presented by Pope Gregory on his first day at the Council of Constance:

First, this synod was and is by right the same synod properly convened in this city of Constance and which had already been properly begun in the city that now houses it.

Furthermore, this sacred council was not dissolved by the departure of our lord the pope, of Constance, and not even by the departure of so many other prelates and other people. But, on the contrary, the council continues in its integrity and authority, even if the opposite has been decreed or may in the future decree it as finished.

The first rule imposed after Gregory officially took over the Council was precisely to decree that the council that was taking place at that time was the same council that had already been initiated previously (obviously without mentioning Pope John XXIII). Now, if there was a need to diligently affirm that this synod was the same synod that had already been established by the council, it is because there were those who disagreed. It is stated that the council continued in integrity and authority, even if the opposite had been decreed, and that the opposite could subsequently be decreed. Now, if Pope John XXIII had abdicated the papal throne by pure will, why would

Why would there be this statement here that the council had not been canceled, as had been decreed? Who would have decreed the end of the council? Wouldn't it have been Pope John XXIII himself who, upon abdicating, would have explained his reasons and then decreed the end of the council? Or simply decreed the end of the council without having abdicated, and his abdication was some political game? Furthermore, the document states that the council was true and valid even if in the future there was some declaration that it had been canceled and was therefore invalid. Who in the future would have the power to decree that the council had actually been closed a day earlier? Wouldn't this be an attribution only possible to John XXIII himself, who presided over the council?

More than that, the document demonstrates that the council continued despite "the pope's trip", but also "despite the departure of so many other prelates and other people", it was not possible to find documentation proving the number of people there. came out together with the abdication of Pope John XXIII.

We have some clues in a letter written by Henrique de Piro²⁷, who was present at the council²⁸. The Cardinal of Cambrai and some other cardinals and prelates would not have appeared at the March 2nd convocation. Then two cardinals and five prelates would have offered to go and call the pope. At the gates they would be called loud and clear. As the pope did not respond, some cardinals and prelates refused to remain at the council, including the patriarch of Antioch and the archbishop of Geneva, who reportedly went in search of the pope, but did not find him. This way they would have decided to postpone the session by one day and everyone would have seen this attempt (an issue that the letter makes a point of highlighting). In the following days, other people left. Depending on the role they had in the council, they needed replacement, as in the case of Bertoldo de Ursins, the council's clerk. On the third day, after the pope's departure, a commission of 5 people was formed to investigate his departure, and

²⁷Little is known about this character. His name appears only once in the acts of the Council, as the author of the suggestion that Jan Hus be handed over to secular power to suffer his punishment.

²⁸Letter cited in LENFANT, Jacques & WHATLEY, Stephen, *The history of the Council of Constance*, p.249

These mounted a case against him, temporarily passing power to Gregory, who would abdicate weeks later in the name of the meeting of cardinals present.²⁹

Even the abdication of Gregory XII is peculiar, since it would not have been done by him in person, nor even through a letter signed by him, but rather by a proxy. This proxy would have been Carlos de Malatesta, prince of Vienna, with his letter being proof of such resignation³⁰.

And it was with great joy that the Emperor gathered the nations in Constance to consult for peace in the Church. He (Gregory XII) is ready, as he always was, for the greater good of God, to renounce his pontificate and his election, which was never worthily legally accepted. In this way he hands over complete power and authority to the assembly gathered here. In this way, since this council was called by the emperor and not by Baldassar Cossa, who called himself John XXIII, and on the condition that Baldassar has already stated that he will no longer preside over the council nor be present at it, he authorizes whatever is necessary to be done. for the general good of the unity of the Church.

Officially Gregory XII abdicates, while officially John XXIII, although recorded as having abdicated on March 2, is considered deposed and subsequently arrested. With the council's vote to declare Pope Benedict XIII a heretic and antipope, we have a church governed by the council, still without a pope.

Although the statements presented above were still made by Gregory XII, we must consider that there was great difficulty in resuming the council after the departure of John XXIII and several bishops and cardinals. This

²⁹Idem, p. 250

³⁰Idem, p. 251

Thus, considering the summary statement that the council that was meeting was still the same council that had previously met as a basic prerogative was essential. See that in the letter from the Prince of Vienna, we even have one more factor to highlight. He is called Baldassar Cossa, his birth name and not his title of John XXIII, and it is officially declared that the person who convened the council was the emperor and not him. In other words, in addition to affirming that the existing council was real and had the power of a council, the effort began to erase the figure of John XXIII, since as convener of the Council and pope, in less than a year he will be a prisoner antipope .

Once it has been established that the council present here was summarily different from what we had already mentioned and that it was having difficulty establishing itself as such, we will continue with the text reopening the council after the "journey" of John XXIII.

Furthermore, this sacred council must not and cannot in any way be dissolved until the present schism is entirely removed, and until the church is reformed in its faith and morals, both its head and its members.

Furthermore, this sacred council cannot in any way be transferred to another location unless it is debated and decided in this present council.

Furthermore, the prelates and other persons who are present at this council may not leave the council before it has ended, except for a justified cause to be examined by the persons who are specifically chosen for this purpose by this council. And if this happens, her reasons are examined and approved, she will only be able to leave after having written permission from the authority established by the council. If any individual leaves, he must automatically give his power to others who will remain, under penalty of law, just as the

Power may be passed on to others appointed by this sacred council.

Those who fail to comply with this law will be persecuted.

By continuing the orders cited here, we have an emphasis not only on making it clear that the council that existed there was the same council previously called by John XXIII, but also the need to guarantee that power would not be withdrawn, in any way, from this council.

When it is decided that the council would not be transferred to another location, this ensures that neither John XXIII nor any other of the current “popes” could call another council or gather members who had left in another city, thus ensuring that while Constance was controlled by the Holy Empire, power over the Church would be in the same hands that was. Likewise, when creating the rule that it was impossible for people to leave the council, unless with very express and handwritten authorizations, this guaranteed that anyone who left the council, whether to seek guidance from another person, or to seek refuge in any other place, that person would automatically be outside the council. This also made it impossible for these people to leave the council and seek to gather “the same council” in another place without the presence of those who were undesirable to them.

The law guaranteeing that the council would remain in session until the schism was resolved served to guarantee the impossibility of Pope John XXIII or anyone else to dissolve the council, since, obviously, those gathered in Constance would never accept leadership outside Constance, and, as long as there was any external leadership, then the council would not cease to exist. In a way it is as if over a period of four years the capital of the church had moved to Constance.

It is also important to emphasize that anyone who abandoned the council would not simply be expelled from the council, but would be persecuted. This great emphasis on preventing new cardinals, bishops or archbishops

abandoning the council can only mean that the situation was not as calm as the acts of the council themselves try to make it appear.

For example, four days after the aforementioned announcements, we have a reformulation of the same rules explained again, this time by the voice of Cardinal Zabarella. Since the beginning of the 15th century, he had fought against the split in the Church, being present at the council of Pisa and participating in the election of John XXIII as the third pope. He was an emissary of the Pope of Pisa to the kings, convincing the participation of bishops and cardinals from both groups in the council of Constance. Therefore a voice that seemed to faithfully represent John XXIII in his absence.³¹, according to Michael Ott³² throughout the council he would have requested a new and urgent papal election to end the interregnum.

However, when we analyze Cardinal Zabarella's words, present below, we will not see such a significant change from what had already been stated four days earlier:

Decrees of the council in authority and integrity, as now read by our Cardinal Zabarella.

By the name of the holy and indivisible Trinity, Father, Son and Holy Spirit, Amen. That holy synod of Constance, which is a general council, for the eradication of the present schism and for bringing unity and reformation to the Church of God, both at its head as in its members, rightfully gathered together by the Holy Spirit to praise the almighty God, orders, defines, decrees, and declares what follows, that the order and reformation of the Church of God may be obtained more easily, more safely, in order to produce more fruits and be more free.

³¹MORRISSEY, Thomas, *The Emperor Elect Sigismund, Cardinal Zabarella and the Council of Constance*, in *The Catholic Historical Review*, vol 69, n.3 p.357

³²OTT, Michael, *Francesco Zabarella*, in *Catholic Encyclopedia*.

First, this synod legitimately gathered by the Holy Spirit really constitutes a General Council, representing the Catholic Church, and that the power of the council emanates immediately from Christ and that everyone, regardless of status and dignity, even if it is the pope himself, is obliged to obey the themes discussed here and have faith in them so that we can eradicate the said schism.

Therefore, our sacred pope and lord, John XXIII, will not be able to move or transfer the Roman curia and its public officers, or other officials, from this city to any other place, neither directly nor indirectly compel people to perform offices that allow them to somehow follow it, without the deliberation and consensus of the same sacred synod. This refers to both officers and offices delivered by those who are absent from this council, as this absence may probably dissolve or do harm to the council. And if he has acted contrary to this in the past, or will act in this way in the future, or if he in the past, now or in the future fulminates any process or mandate or makes any ecclesiastical censure or any type of penalty to any of the officers present here or if in any way act or speak any censure or penalty to any person present at the council, we must consider such orders, words or actions null and void and that none of their penalties be obeyed, and that they be considered invalid. The so-called officials are indispensable for carrying out the work being done in Constance and will carry out their work freely, as they did previously, even before this synod was convened in this so-called city.

(...)

Furthermore, in order to maintain our unity, new cardinals cannot be created, and they will be considered fraudulent,

No matter the reason, any people who come to the council saying they have recently been made cardinals by anyone. This sacred council declares that these people should not be treated as cardinals, nor publicly recognized as such, no new cardinals should be recognized from the day of our lord the pope's departure from Constance.

Although the speech was made by Cardinal Zabarella, it only reinforces the lack of power of Pope John XXIII, and the maintenance of power in the hands of the council, reaffirming that the pope does not have the power to cancel the council, move it or do anything against him.

The big difference we see here is the addition of one more factor, the impossibility of the pope creating new cardinals. For this statement to be made, it is very likely that the pope created new cardinals and sent them to the council, in this way, with a large number of new cardinals faithful to him, he could probably change the vote of the council in his favor, or in favor of his ideas, but, by prohibiting not only the emergence of new cardinals, but ensuring that no new cardinals could have been made since the pope's departure from Constance, this would guarantee that power would remain firmly in the hands of the Council.

It is possible that Cardinal Zabarella was simply chosen as the spokesperson for these rules and not that he participated in their creation, since according to the acts of the council he only read the resolutions. Perhaps the choice to use as spokesman a cardinal who was truly faithful to John XXIII was made to ensure that the other cardinals faithful to him realized how the council really took control of what was happening, smoothing out any and all corners that could be used by him to regain power.

Even so, there is an important factor to be noted: in the speech four days earlier, neither the title of pope nor the papal name was used when speaking.

Speaking of John XXIII, on the contrary, it is stated that it was the emperor and not him who convened the council. However, here, at least, the statement returns that he was the real pope, he just did not have the power to define anything that was contrary to the council.

From March 30, 1415 to May 2, 1415, the council had 7 more sessions. All of these were brief and contained restatements similar to the rules already presented here, ensuring that John XXIII had no power over decisions, reaffirming that the present council was the same as the one initiated previously, and closing other possible openings that could be used to diminish the council's legitimacy. .

Pope Gregory XII, of Rome, who had assumed the Council and then abdicated the throne, assumed the role of president of the Council during the following years, until on October 18, 1417 he died, immediately after his death. , although he was not officially considered pope, a conclave was called, and on November 11, 1417, Martin V was elected pope, thus unifying the three papacies.

Although official unification took place in 1417, Benedict XIII did not accept the Council's resolution, continuing his resistance, even though little by little the Avignon lineage was losing its power. After his death in 1423, a new conclave was held following the Avignon lineage, which now took refuge in Aragon, the last kingdom to offer support. From this, the Avignonian pope Clement VIII was elected, who will reign until 1429. He will abdicate his throne, but even so, we will have the last election of this lineage, choosing Benedict XIV as pontiff, at this time, without the support of any secular kingdom, the lineage it simply falls into oblivion.

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